

Original Article

Publication History:

Published 1/1/2021

DOI:

10.5281/zenodo.4430243

Corresponding Author:

Dr. Hira Ahsan
Fatima Jinnah Medical
University Lahore
hiraahsan710@gmail.com

Cite this article as:

Ahmad W, Abbas S,
Ahsan H. Acute tonsillitis
and its relationship with
complete blood count. Int.
J. Med. Dent. Allied Health
Sci. 2020;3(1). 742-46

© Copyright 2020

This is an open access article
distributed under the terms of the
Creative Commons Attribution
License CC-BY 4.0., which
permits unrestricted use,
distribution, and reproduction in
any medium, provided the
original author and source are
credited.

**ACUTE TONSILLITIS AND ITS
RELATIONSHIP WITH COMPLETE
BLOOD COUNT**

AUTHORS:

1. DR. WASEEM AHMAD, THQ HOSPITAL GOJRA
2. DR. SARTAJ ABBAS, DHQ HOSPITAL VEHARI
3. DR. HIRA AHSAN, FATIMA JINNAH MEDICAL
UNIVERSITY LAHORE

ABSTRACT:

A complete blood count (CBC), also known as a full blood count (FBC), is a set of medical laboratory tests that provide information about the cells in a person's blood. The CBC indicates the counts of white blood cells, red blood cells and platelets, the concentration of hemoglobin, and the hematocrit (the volume percentage of red blood cells). This cross-sectional study was conducted among the patients presenting in the medical outdoor department of different hospitals. Name, age, gender and history and duration of acute tonsillitis were noted on a predefined proforma. Complete blood count reports of all the patients were taken from the lab. All the data was entered and analyzed with SPSS Ver. 23.0. A total of 50 patients with history of acute tonsillitis were included in this study i.e., 25 males (50%) and 25 females (50%). The mean age of the patients was 31.34±5.21 years. In 23 cases of acute tonsillitis, CBC revealed raised ESR and CRP. Anemia was found in five cases.

**Keyword: Acute Tonsillitis, Complete Blood
Count**

INTRODUCTION:

A complete blood count (CBC), also known as a full blood count (FBC), is a set of medical laboratory tests that provide information about the cells in a person's blood. The CBC indicates the counts of white blood cells, red blood cells and platelets, the concentration of hemoglobin, and the hematocrit (the volume percentage of red blood cells). The red blood cell indices, which indicate the average size and hemoglobin content of red blood cells, are also reported, and a white blood cell differential, which counts the different types of white blood cells, may be included. The CBC is often carried out as part of a medical assessment and can be used to monitor health or diagnose diseases. The results are interpreted by comparing them to reference ranges, which vary with sex and age. Conditions like anemia and thrombocytopenia are defined by abnormal complete blood count results. The red blood cell indices can provide information about the cause of a person's anemia such as iron deficiency and vitamin B12 deficiency, and the results of the white blood cell differential can help to diagnose viral, bacterial and parasitic infections and blood disorders like leukemia. Not all results falling outside of the reference range require medical intervention.

The CBC is performed using basic laboratory equipment or an automated hematology analyzer, which counts cells and collects information on their size and structure. The concentration of hemoglobin is measured, and the red blood cell indices are calculated from measurements of red blood cells and hemoglobin. Manual tests can be used to independently confirm abnormal results. Approximately 10–25% of samples require a manual blood smear review, in which the blood is stained and viewed under a microscope to verify that the analyzer results are consistent with the appearance of the cells and to look for abnormalities. The hematocrit can be determined manually by centrifuging the sample and measuring the proportion of red blood cells, and in laboratories without access to automated instruments, blood cells are counted under the microscope using a hemocytometer.

In 1852, Karl Vierordt published the first procedure for performing a blood count, which involved spreading a known volume of blood on a microscope slide and counting every cell. The invention of the hemocytometer in 1874 by Louis-Charles Malassez simplified the microscopic analysis of blood cells, and in the late 19th century, Paul Ehrlich and Dmitri Leonidovich Romanowsky developed techniques for staining white and red blood cells that are still used to examine blood smears. Automated methods for measuring hemoglobin were developed in the 1920s, and Maxwell Wintrobe introduced the Wintrobe hematocrit method in 1929, which in turn allowed him to define the red blood cell indices. A landmark in the automation of blood cell counts was the Coulter principle, which was patented by Wallace H. Coulter in 1953. The Coulter principle uses electrical impedance measurements to count blood cells and determine their sizes; it is a technology that remains in use in many automated analyzers. Further research in the 1970s involved the use of optical measurements to count and identify cells, which enabled the automation of the white blood cell differential (1-3). The objective of this study is to see the relationship between complete blood count and acute tonsillitis.

MATERIAL AND METHODS:

This cross-sectional study was conducted among the patients presenting in the medical outdoor department of different hospitals. Name, age, gender and history and duration of acute tonsillitis were noted on a predefined proforma. Complete blood count reports of all the patients were taken from the lab. All the data was entered and analyzed with SPSS Ver. 23.0. The quantitative variables were presented as mean and standard deviation. The qualitative variables were presented as frequency and percentages.

RESULTS:

A total of 50 patients with history of acute tonsillitis were included in this study i.e., 25 males (50%) and 25 females (50%). The mean age of the patients

was 31.34 ± 5.21 years. In 23 cases of acute tonsillitis, CBC revealed raised ESR and CRP. Anemia was found in five cases.

DISCUSSION:

Tonsillitis is inflammation of the tonsils in the upper part of the throat. Tonsillitis is a type of pharyngitis that typically comes on fast (rapid onset). Symptoms may include sore throat, fever, enlargement of the tonsils, trouble swallowing, and large lymph nodes around the neck. Complications include peritonsillar abscess. Tonsillitis is most commonly caused by a viral infection and about 5% to 40% of cases are caused by a bacterial infection. When caused by the bacterium group A streptococcus, it is referred to as strep throat. Rarely bacteria such as *Neisseria gonorrhoeae*, *Corynebacterium diphtheriae*, or *Haemophilus influenzae* may be the cause. Typically the infection is spread between people through the air. A scoring system, such as the Centor score, may help separate possible causes. Confirmation may be by a throat swab or rapid strep test.

Treatment efforts involve improving symptoms and decreasing complications. Paracetamol (acetaminophen) and ibuprofen may be used to help with pain. If strep throat is present the antibiotic penicillin by mouth is generally recommended. In those who are allergic to penicillin, cephalosporins or macrolides may be used. In children with frequent episodes of tonsillitis, tonsillectomy modestly decreases the risk of future episodes. About 7.5% of people have a sore throat in any three-month period and 2% of people visit a doctor for tonsillitis each year. It is most common in school-aged children and typically occurs in the colder months of fall and winter. Most people recover with or without medication. In 40% of people, symptoms resolve within three days, and in 80% symptoms resolve within one week, regardless of whether streptococcus is present. Antibiotics decrease symptom duration by approximately sixteen hours (4-6).

REFERENCES:

1. Ciesla, B (2018). Hematology in Practice (3 ed.). F. A. Davis Company. ISBN 978-0-8036-6825-6.
2. Da Costa, L (2015). "Digital image analysis of blood cells". Clinics in Laboratory Medicine. 35(1): 105–122. doi:10.1016/j.cl.2014.10.005. ISSN 0272-2712. PMID 25676375.
3. Dasgupta, A; Sepulveda, JL (2013). Accurate Results in the Clinical Laboratory: A Guide to Error Detection and Correction. Elsevier. ISBN 978-0-12-415858-0.
4. Davis, JD (1995). "The evolution of the progressive-era hemocytometer". Caduceus: A Humanities Journal for Medicine and the Health Sciences. 11 (3): 164–183. PMID 8680947.
5. DiGregorio, RV; Green-Hernandez, C; Holzemer, SP (2014). Primary Care: An Interprofessional Perspective (2 ed.). Springer Publishing Company. ISBN 978-0-8261-7148-1.
6. Dooley, EK; Ringler, RL (2012). "Prenatal care: touching the future". Primary Care: Clinics in Office Practice. 39 (1): 17–37. doi:10.1016/j.pop.2011.11.002. ISSN 0095-4543. PMID 22309579.